

Device simulations of NPN AlGaIn/GaN Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor using Medici

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Abstract—This paper investigates NPN AlGaIn/GaN HBT by doing two-dimensional device simulation with the help of CAD tool Medici. In designing emitter, polarization effects were considered which leads to positive sheet charge at emitter-base junction and negative sheet charge within the emitter. Gummel plot of the device is plotted and the current gain of more than a hundred is found at a lower values of collector current in the range of microampere, however current gain decreases rapidly in order to achieve a decent collector current in order of milliampere. A high current gain cut-off frequency of 2.5 GHz was also found and a plot of current gain cut-off frequency and collector current was also plotted. Carrier and impurity concentration plot along with the electric field plot were also presented. All the restraints which are keeping us away from a high power, high amplifier device were also discussed.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent times, advancements made in the field of wireless communications has urged the demand of solid state amplifiers with high efficiency and power. Current technologies available with semiconductor materials like GaAs, SiGe etc. are not able to cope up with these requirements. So we have to look at other semiconductor materials and one such material that comes to the picture is GaN. GaN based devices are getting so much attention because of their wide bandgap and saturated electron velocities which leads to higher critical breakdown field/electric field. For GaN, $V_{sat} = 2 \times 10^7 \text{ cm/s}$ [1], $E_g = 3.4 \text{ eV}$ and $E_{critical} = 2 \text{ MV/cm}$ [2]. So we can use these devices in high power and high temperature application. Interest in investigating GaN heterojunction bipolar transistor is propelled by the various advantages that HBT's enjoy over HEMT's. Compared with FET's, HBT's employs vertical current transport, so we can get higher power density by utilizing the area of wafer efficiently. Secondly, HBT's offers high linearity at high level of power and low phase noise which is necessary for high power amplifier. GaN based HBT's has been developed by various techniques in the literature [3] [4] [5] [6] and the results are still introductory.

In this paper we will design a AlGaIn/GaN NPN HBT and will analyze the device using a two-dimensional simulator Medici. Devices demonstrated in the literature [3] [7] is taken as a reference for the design of the HBT considered in this paper. The paper also presents issues to the development of GaN HBT's. Section 2 of the paper will present device design while section 3 will focus on simulation. DC I-V characteristics of the device will be described in section 4

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Fig. 1. Layer structure of $\text{Al}_{0.1}\text{GaIn}/\text{GaN}$ Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor

Fig. 2. Cross-section of the simulated AlGaIn/GaN Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor

of the paper and section 5 will concentrate on conclusion and future works with GaN bipolar transistors.

II. DEVICE DETAILS

Device structure used in these simulations was referred from literature [3] [7]. Layer structure of AlGaIn/GaN HBT along with the cross-section of the simulated AlGaIn/GaN HBT is shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively. The emitter is n-type doped AlGaIn with the mole fraction of aluminum taken as 0.1. N-type doped GaN is used as an emitter contact layer and p-type doped GaN is taken as a base with a width of 0.1 micrometer. GaN of width 0.02 micrometer is used as a spacer in between emitter and base with low concentration of n-type dopants. The collector is 0.5 micrometer wide with unintentionally doped (UID) n-type GaN with a donor concentration of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The low doping of collector is also beneficial as it increases the breakdown voltage of the collector-base junction, reduce collector capacitance and reduce the widening of the base-collector space charge region into the base (which is also known as early effect). The sub-collector is GaN doped n-type with $N_D = 5 \times 10^{17}$. Heterojunctions allow us to dope the base heavily reducing the base resistance without compromising the current gain. Similar idea has been incorporated in the device design in which emitter is doped n-type with $N_D = 2 \times 10^{17}$ whereas

base is doped p-type with $N_A = 4 \times 10^{17}$, however GaN is doped p-type with magnesium which is a deep acceptor [8] and leads to incomplete ionization. Design of emitter is done in a way that we get low hole injection from base to emitter in a forward bias operation without compromising with vertical electron conductivity. Emitter is lightly doped than base to reduce junction capacitance.

We have to consider polarization charge while we are dealing with III-N based devices. There are two types of polarization: 1. Spontaneous polarization (P_{sp}) 2. Piezoelectric polarization (P_{pz}). We get P_{sp} when the center of positive charges and negative charges are non-coincidental. P_{pz} is the result of strain which is due to lattice mismatch. There is a large crystal lattice mismatch between GaN and its Al alloys which is getting combined with strong polarity of wurtzite GaN crystal and gives us a polarization charge which is in the range of doping concentration. Total polarization charge as a function of change in Al mole fraction is given as Δx . The equation to calculate polarization charge [9] [10] [11] [12] can be given as $P(\Delta x) = P_{sp}(\Delta x) + 2(e_{31} + \frac{c_{13}}{c_{33}}e_{33})E(\Delta x)$ where $E(\Delta x) = \frac{a' - a(\Delta x)}{a} = 0.0241\Delta x$, a' = strained lattice constant, a = relaxed lattice constant, e_{31} and e_{33} = elastic constant. In the emitter of the device Al composition gets change by 10% (0.1 mole) then the polarization charge density is equal to $6 \times 10^{-7} C/cm^2$ and the values used to calculate it is shown in Table 1. However, we can reduce this charge density by changing an alloy composition gradually.

In design of emitter we have to consider polarization because of change in alloy composition due to which, positive/donor like sheet charge gets created at emitter-base junction and pulls down the conduction band at hetero-interface. On the other hand polarization increases the barrier at GaN:Si/Al_{0.1}GaN interface within an emitter because negative/acceptor like sheet charge gets created there. These Effects on energy band diagram due to polarization charge is shown in Fig 4, and we can easily compare it with the energy band diagram of AlGaIn/GaN HBT without polarization effect shown in Fig 3. However, while designing the collector we always have to consider the trade-off between the electron transit time and breakdown voltage. Electrons gets transport vertically in the collector region and laterally in sub-collector region to collector contacts. The carrier and impurity profile is shown in Fig 5, indubitably holes have a high concentration in the base region whereas electrons have higher concentration in emitter and collector region.

TABLE I
VALUES USED TO CALCULATE POLARIZATION CHARGE IN Al_xGa_{1-x}N

Constant	value(x)	Units
$P_{sp}(\delta x)$	$-0.052 \times \text{Change in Al mole fraction}$	C/m^2
$e_{31}(x)$	$-0.49 - (0.11 \times \text{mole fraction of Al})$	C/m^2
$e_{33}(x)$	$0.73(1 + \text{mole fraction of Al})$	C/m^2
$c_{13}(x)$	$103 + 5(\text{mole fraction of Al})$	GPa
$c_{33}(x)$	$405 - 27(\text{mole fraction of Al})$	GPa
$a(x)$	$0.3189 - 0.0077(\text{mole fraction of Al})$	nm

Fig. 3. Band diagram of AlGaIn/GaN heterojunction bipolar transistor without considering polarization effects.

Fig. 4. Band diagram of AlGaIn/GaN heterojunction bipolar transistor considering polarization effects.

Fig. 5. Carrier and Doping concentration of AlGaIn/GaN HBT

III. ALGAN/GAN HBT SIMULATIONS

The AlGaIn/GaN HBT studied in this work was simulated in a commercial simulator (Medici). However, Medici does

not have GaN as a predefined semiconductor material so all the material regions were defined as GaAs and later all the material properties and mobility parameters were redefined according to GaN. For simulation, device was defined as a rectangular mesh of contiguous nodes. The cross-section of the device was defined with vertically etched layers which are similar to the devices obtained using dry etching which can be seen in Fig 2. Physical effects which were taken care during simulations were thermionic emission, concentration dependent carrier recombination by shockley- Read-Hall mechanisms, bandgap narrowing and field mobility characteristics. Various physical parameter like energy band diagram, electron velocities, electrical field were plotted at a specific bias. The effect of changing base doping on the energy band diagram was also seen and our results infer that if the base doping is very high then the device will go towards degeneration and the band bending becomes a lot linear rather than a curve. The two-dimensional plot of electric field is shown in Fig 6, and maximum electric field can be seen in the region between emitter and base which is much smaller than critical electric field (electric field for impact ionization avalanche breakdown). Leakage currents were also seen with low voltages and further discussion on them has been done in section 4. A severe degradation of current gain is also seen and plot between current gain and base-emitter voltage is also plotted which can be seen in Fig 8. The plot for current gain cut-off frequency vs collector current is also plotted and is shown in Fig 9.

IV. DC I-V CHARACTERISTICS

The DC I-V characteristics were acquired by calculating the collector current and the base current with the increase in base-emitter voltage steadily. We can use these characteristics for better assimilation of the working of AlGaIn/GaN HBT's and also to understand the limitations of the device. Gummel plot is shown in Fig 7, and we can infer that the collector current increases rapidly when V_{BE} gets greater than 1.4 V and current gain vs base-emitter voltage is shown in Fig 8. We can infer that current gain increases at low voltage between the base and the emitter and decreases when the voltage increases. The variation of current gain is thoroughly explained in part B of this section. The plot for current gain cut-off frequency is also plotted and can be seen in Figure 9, and frequency response is comprehensively discussed in part C of this section. To understand DC I-V characteristics better we have to look at the theory behind the current in HBT [13]. Unlike Homojunction, current in heterojunction is because of thermionic emission over abrupt barrier. We can not apply drift and diffusion model because ΔE_c & ΔE_v are much greater than KT (which is the thermal voltage). On the other hand current gain in common emitter configuration can be defined as ratio of (output current) collector current to the (input current) base current.

A. Current gain

As defined earlier current gain can be given by ratio between collector current to the base current in common emitter

Fig. 6. Electric field vs Distance in AlGaIn/GaN HBT

Fig. 7. Gummel Plot of AlGaIn/GaN HBT

Fig. 8. Current Gain vs Base-Emitter Voltage HBT

configuration. AlGaIn/GaN HBT's are suffering from leakage currents (I_{CBO} and I_{CEO}) at low voltage between base to emitter as shown in Fig 8. This can be one of the reason because of which at low current level we can observe very high current gain at low voltage [14]. We have to also consider that in reality this much gain can't be achieved by the device because GaN is doped p-type with magnesium which is a deep acceptor and leads to incomplete ionization. Effect of the leakage current gets decrease when current increase and gain decrease. On the other hand reason behind the low current gain at high current level is Kirk effect. Due to Kirk effect, width of the collector-base space charge region gets decrease and neutral base gets widen because emitter is lightly doped and due to that most of the depletion happens at the emitter side. Base layer widening decrease the current gain at high currents and frequency response of the transistor also gets decrease.

B. Frequency Response

The plot for current gain cut-off frequency is shown in Fig 9. The effect on frequency response of the device is discussed in this section if changes are made in emitter, base or collector. We can define current gain cut-off frequency as $f_T = \frac{1}{2\pi(\tau_E + \tau_B + \tau_{CSCL} + \tau_C)}$ where $\tau_E =$ Emitter charging time, $\tau_B =$ Base transient time, $\tau_{CSCL} =$ Collector transient time and $\tau_C =$ Collector charging time. The maximum Current gain cut-off frequency of 2.5 Ghz is shown by device seen in figure 9. Whereas maximum oscillation frequency can be given as $f_{MAX} = \sqrt{\frac{f_T}{8\pi R_B C_{BC}}}$ where $R_B =$ Parasitic base resistance and $C_{BC} =$ Base-collector capacitance. Gain of the transistor decreases at higher frequencies because finite time is needed to move charges to the various parts of the transistor. In a uniform base region current flows primarily by diffusion across the quasi neutral base but to decrease base transit time and increase current gain cut-off frequency we have to incorporate drift transport mechanism to accelerate the electrons across the base region. This is can be achieved by doping gradient or by changing the bandgap of the semiconductor across the base region. Whereas we can decrease the collector transit time by increasing the donor concentration in the collector region but this will decrease the breakdown voltage. So there is always a trade off between the breakdown voltage and frequency response.

By increasing the base doping of AlGaIn/GaN HBT's, we can increase f_T because charging time gets reduce and increase f_{MAX} because base resistance gets reduce. When we increase emitter doping, value of current gain gets reduce but f_T and f_{MAX} gets increase. If we decrease the width of the collector region, there is no change in value of gain and f_T but f_{MAX} gets decrease because base-collector capacitance increases.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The DC I-V characteristics and current gain cut-off frequency of AlGaIn/GaN HBT's are discussed. We are getting high current gain at low current level due to the leakage currents and low current gain at high current level due to the

Fig. 9. Current gain cut-off frequency vs collector current in AlGaIn/GaN HBT

Kirk effect. Result shown by the device are quite remarkable for power and amplification purposes but some restrains in fabrication and not having a good p-type donor for GaN compound semiconductor keeping us away from a high power, high amplifier device. However, PNP devices are also seen as an alternative because n type dopant is shallow, so conductivity of n-type base is high. At the same time in PNP AlGaIn/GaN we have to dope emitter very strongly because of the deep acceptor in the emitter. Due to this we get very narrow depletion region and parasitic base-emitter capacitance gets increase. In the future, efforts will be made on improving current gain at high current level along with all the other restrains thus improving an effort towards having a good RF device.

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REFERENCES

- [1] U. V. Bhapkar and M. S. Shur, "Monte Carlo calculations of velocity-field characteristics of wurtzite GaN," *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 82, pp. 1649–1655, 1997.
- [2] J. Kolnik, J. H. Ogunzman, K. F. Brennan, W. Rongping, and P. P. Ruden, "Monte Carlo calculation of electron initiated impact ionisation in bulk zinc-blende and wurtzite GaN," *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 81, pp. 726–733, 1997.
- [3] L. S. McCarthy, P. Kozodoy, M. J. W. Rodwell, S. P. DenBaars, and U. K. Mishra, "AlGaIn/GaN Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 277–279, 1999.
- [4] "A first look at AlGaIn/GaN HBT's," *Compound semicond.*, vol. 4, no. 8, pp. 16–18, 1998.
- [5] J. B. Limb, L. McCarthy, P. Kozodoy, H. Xing, J. Ibbetson, Y. Smorchkova, S. P. DenBaars, and U. K. Mishra, "AlGaIn/GaN HBT's using regrown emitter," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 35, no. 19, pp. 1671–1673, 1999.
- [6] J. Han, A. G. Baca, R. J. Shul, C. J. Willison, L. Zhang, F. Ren, A. P. Zhang, G. T. Dang, S. M. Donovan, X. A. Cao, H. Cho, K. B. Jung, C. R. Abernathy, S. J. Pearton, and R. G. Wilson, "Growth and fabrication of GaN/AlGaIn heterojunction bipolar transistor," *applied physics letter*, vol. 74, no. 18, pp. 2702–2704, 1999.

- [7] E. Alekseev and D. Pavlidis, "DC and high-frequency performance of AlGaIn/GaN Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor," *Solid State electronics*, vol. 44, pp. 245–252, 2000.
- [8] P.Kozodoy, "Heavy doping effects in Mg-doped GaN," *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 87, pp. 1832–1835, 2000.
- [9] O. Ambacher, B. Foutz, J. R. Shealy, N. G. Weimann, K.Chu, M. Murphy, A. J. Sierakowski, W. J. Schaff, L. F. Easrman, R.Dimitrov, A. Mitchell, and M. Stutzmann, "Two dimensional electron gases induced by spontaneous and piezoelectric polarisation in undoped and doped AlGaIn/GaN heterostructures," *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 87, no. 1, pp. 334–344, 2000.
- [10] O. Ambacher, J. Smart, J. R. Shealy, N. G. Weimann, K. Chu, M. Murphy, W. J. Schaff, L. F. Eastman, R. Dimitrov, L. Wittmer, M.Stutzmann, W. Reiger, and J. Hilsenbeck, "Two dimensional electron gases induced by spontaneous and piezoelectric polarisation charges in N- and Ga-face AlGaIn/GaN heterostructures," *Journal of applied Physics*, vol. 85, no. 6, pp. 3222–3236, 1999.
- [11] "Spontaneous polarisation and piezoelectric constants of III-V nitrides," *Physical Review B(Condensed matter)*, vol. 56, no. 16, pp. R10024–R10027, 1997.
- [12] "Elastic properties of zinc-blende and wurtzite AlN,GaN and InN," *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 82, no. 6, pp. 2833–2839, 1997.
- [13] R. S. Muller, T. I. Kamins, and M. Chan, "Heterojunctions," in *Device Electronics for integrated circuits*, 2003, pp. 251–256.
- [14] H. Xing, D. Jena, M. J. W. Rodwell, and U. K. Mishra, "Explanation of Anomalously high Current gain Observed in GaN Based Bipolar Transistor," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 316–318, 2003.

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